

Research Article

**Mental Stress and Sleep quality for frontline healthcare workers
exposed to the outbreak of COVID-19**

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Abstract

During the early stage of the COVID-19 pandemic, anxiety symptoms were reported in 28.8% and depressive symptoms in 16.5% of the general population in China [21].

In the literature review [22-25], no difference was found between the units where the medical personnel were working during the pandemic and their anxiety levels. The current study is considered that the anxiety of medical personnel increased due to having to provide simultaneous treatment and care to both adults and children, who are very different from each other in terms of their characteristics and needs.

A total of 120 health workers participated in this study. Male participants are 50(41.66%) and female participants are 70(78.33%), in which 100(83.33%) were married and 20(16.66%) were Unmarried having the work experience upto 2 years were 40(33.33%) and above 2 years experience were 80(66.66%). Among them having nursing education 62(51.66%) and medical education were 58(48.33%).

The prevalence of occupational stress among CHWs was found Feel tired (43.33%) followed by emotionally exhausted (26.66%) and Feeling weak (30%) stress in the present study. Although these findings were matched on the level of stress, statistics between these two studies differ. However, no evidence of association was observed between occupational stress and other socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, education, job position, and working year. Occupational stress was significantly associated with various stressors such as under Feel tired, emotionally exhausted and Feeling weak.

Keywords: Occupational stress, COVID-19 pandemic, medical education, Mental Stress and Sleep quality.

Introduction

Even while the COVID-19 outbreak has had a direct or indirect influence on every business, the problem has exacerbated the already overburdened health-care systems in many countries. The virus's ongoing spread in all settings had a significant impact on health-care delivery, especially in the early phases. It posed challenges for medical supply management, facility use, and health human resource management. A new coronavirus known as SARS-CoV-2 was discovered in December 2019, which sparked a global epidemic and put further strain on healthcare professionals (HCPs). HCPs faced high levels of stress, unpredictable schedules with frequent and lengthy work shifts, and situations outside of their usual employment [1– 3].

The COVID-19 outbreak appears to have considerably affected health-care delivery, particularly in low-income countries. In addition to the direct impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, indirect strain on health systems and overstretch of others also contributed to the disruption. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the flaws of the present healthcare system. The COVID-19 pandemic has interrupted both preventative and therapeutic services for communicable and noncommunicable illnesses. Many of essential services have been delayed by the healthcare facilities, patients were also unable to attend follow-ups and acute care visits due to the fear and anxiety they experienced during the pandemic waves[4-10].

Community Health Workers (CHWs) are community individuals who have been chosen to work closely with persons supported by the health system but are not necessarily employees of the organization. The primary advantage of having a CHW is that people readily accept them. In India, the notion of CHW has a long and rich history; there are four types of CHWs: ASHA (Accredited Social Health Activist), ANM (Auxiliary nurse midwife), Anganwadi worker, and multi-purpose health assistant[11]. CHW are assigned various responsibilities under

national health programs. With the declaration of the COVID-19 pandemic, additional duties are assigned to ASHA workers and ANM, such as contact tracing, community surveillance, implementing home quarantine, and identification of high-risk groups (HRG) and probable cases.[12]

The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the cause of the continuing worldwide coronavirus disease pandemic, also known as COVID-19. As of right moment, COVID-19 has spread to 223 nations and territories, raising serious concerns for global health. [13].

Both the care provided to patients and the quality of life of healthcare professionals can be impacted by their health. Considering the intense workload and quick changes in this industry, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought this problem to light. Healthcare professionals have always been overextended physically, mentally, and emotionally. [14]; Still, things like pandemics and breakouts need to be taken seriously. [15].

Systematic reviews of healthcare workers during global infectious disease outbreaks, for example, COVID-19, SARS, H1N1, EBOLA and MERS found high incidences of burnout (28–32%), acute stress (30%), post-traumatic stress disorder (13%) and insomnia (40%) [15-17].

Occupational stress is another issue that can lead to both physical and emotional weariness. Theories about stress emphasize the influence of psychic factors on bodily functions [18], resulting in a reaction to the stressor that is either positive or negative, depending on how people's resources and abilities balance perceived demands. This can have an effect on mental or physical health. [19].

Materials and Methods

Study Design

The research is a cross-sectional study/survey, and The data were collected online via WhatsApp using the survey method. The questionnaire was shared in the Whatsapp groups in which there were chief physicians of all emergency services, which took place

between December 01, 2021, and June 15, 2022. Chief physicians were asked to share this questionnaire with all of the healthcare personnel in their departments. This study was followed the principles of the guidelines of the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology [20].

Stress Index

A well developed and widely used OSI in the Indian context (Srivastava and Singh 1981) was chosen to assess the occupational stress of the subjects. The questionnaire consists of 46 statements with five alternative responses based on 5-point Likert scale, for example, score 5 for strongly agree, score 4 for agree, score 3 for undecided, score 2 is for disagreeing, and score 1 for strongly disagree. The total score on this scale was considered for the assessment of occupational stress. Higher the score on OSI, higher is the level of stress.

Participants

The study was approved by the institutional review board of RK Singh Hospital and Institute of Medical Sciences, Ragauli Karvi, - 210205, India, and Before the online enrollment process began, every participant gave their written, electronic consent, which was included in the questionnaire. Self-reported online questionnaire survey was conducted.

Inclusion criteria included voluntary participation, pursuing a health profession in local hospitals. Individuals who did not reply to the questionnaire and declined to participate after being invited were not included in the study.

Included with the survey was an information sheet that provided a thorough description of the goal of the research. The survey's participants were unable to go on to the following question

for a number of questions until they had responded.

Emails containing the study's questionnaire were distributed to all staff members working in the public and private hospitals and healthcare facilities in the RK Singh Hospital and Institute of Medical Sciences, Ragauli Karvi, - 210205, India. Frontline healthcare workers (FLHCWs) and non-frontline healthcare workers (NFLHCWs) were the two categories into which the participants were divided based on their workplace.

The questionnaire included questions about the participants' age, gender, marital status, number of children, education, career, job location, specialization, and experience working with COVID patients and in an intensive care unit (ICU). The structured questionnaire sought to collect information about stress and sleep quality.

The investigation was performed with the involvement of 120 medical personnel.

Statistical analysis

The data were coded, entered, and analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 20. The level of $P = 0.05$ was taken as statistically significant. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize participants' socio-demographic factors.

RESULTS

A total of 120 health workers participated in this study. Male participants are 50(41.66%) and female participants are 70(78.33%), in which 100(83.33%) were married and 20(16.66%) were Unmarried having the work experience upto 2 years were 40(33.33%) and above 2 years experience were 80(66.66%). Among them having nursing education 62(51.66%) and medical education were 58(48.33%).

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on socio-demographic and work related characteristics, with relate to occupational stress score on OSI.

Characteristics	N=120	Occupational Stress			P value
		Low(%)	Moderate(%)	High(%)	
Age	15-50				0.16
Sex					
Male	50 (41.66%)	17(34%)	20(40%)	13(26%)	
Female	70 (58.33%)	30(42.85%)	35(50%)	05(7.14%)	
Marital status					0.5
Married	100 (83.33%)	35(35%)	60(60%)	05(5%)	
Unmarried	20 (16.66%)	10(50%)	7(35%)	03(15%)	
Work Experience					0.16
1-2 years	40 (33.33%)	9(22.5%)	20(50%)	11(27.5%)	
Above 2 years	80 (66.66%)	31(38.75%)	40(50%)	09(11.25%)	
Education					0.21
Nursing	62 (51.66%)	21(33.87%)	35(56.45%)	04(6.45%)	
Medical	58 (48.33%)	20(34.48%)	30(51.72%)	08(13.79%)	
Occupation					0.2
Nurse	62 (51.66%)	21(33.87%)	35(56.45%)	04(6.45%)	
Physical therapist	15 (12.5%)	5(33.33%)	9(60%)	01(26.66%)	
Physician	10 (8.33%)	4(40%)	5(50%)	1(10%)	
Dentist	8 (6.66%)	2(25%)	4(50%)	2(25%)	
Other	25 (20.83%)	1(4%)	20(80%)	4(16%)	
Working style					0.7
Daytime shift	45(37.5%)	15(33.33%)	20(44.44%)	10(22.22%)	
Day and night shifts	65(54.16%)	20(30.76%)	30(46.15%)	15(23.07%)	
24 hour shift	10(8.33%)	2(20%)	5(50%)	3(30%)	
Working year in the ICU					0.15
≤1 year	29(24.16%)	9(31.09%)	15(51.72%)	6(20.68%)	
2≤ years ≤9	38(31.66%)	10(26.31%)	20(52.63)	8(21.05%)	
More than 09 years	53(44.16%)	13(24.52%)	30(56.6%)	10(18.86%)	
Workplace					0.23
Hospital OPD	74 (61.66%)	25(3378%)	35(47.29%)	14(18.91%)	
ICU	46 (38.33%)	12(26.08%)	30(65.41%)	4(8.7%)	

Table 1: Distribution of respondents based on Stress and sleep quality.

Characteristics	N=120	P value
Sleep Quality		0.25
Good	35 (29.16%)	
Moderate	25 (20.83%)	
poor	60 (50%)	
Stress		
Feel tired (Work Overload)	52 (43.33%)	
emotionally exhausted	32 (26.66%)	
Feeling weak	36 (30%)	

The prevalence of occupational stress among CHWs was found Feel tired (43.33%) followed by emotionally exhausted (26.66%) and Feeling weak (30%) stress in the present study.

Although these findings were matched on the level of stress, statistics between these two studies differ.

However, no evidence of association was observed between occupational stress and other socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, education, job position, and working year. Occupational stress was significantly associated with various stressors such as under Feel tired, emotionally exhausted and Feeling weak.

Study Limitations

The study has some limitations. Although the surveys were issued to all emergency services, only voluntary participants completed them. Individuals with poor anxiety and sleep quality may have been more inclined to complete the surveys. During the COVID-19 pandemic, there is no clear causal association between certain features of healthcare personnel and their sleep quality levels.

Because there is no control group, it is impossible to evaluate if the same causes that cause anxiety and sleep disturbances in the general population also cause sleep disturbance in healthcare workers during the pandemic.

The weaknesses identified in the study include:

1. Self-reporting: The study relied on participants' self-reporting of stress levels and sleep quality. Self-report measures are subjective and can be influenced by recall bias or social desirability bias. Participants may have provided inaccurate or incomplete information, which could affect the validity of the results.
2. Cross-sectional design: The study was cross-sectional, which means that data was collected at a single point in time. This design does not allow for establishing causal relationships between variables. It only provides information about associations or correlations between stress and sleep quality. Longitudinal or experimental

designs would be needed to establish causal relationships.

3. Potential confounding variables: Cross-sectional studies may be susceptible to confounding variables that can influence the relationship between stress and sleep quality. Factors such as age, gender, socioeconomic status, and other personal characteristics or lifestyle factors could affect both stress levels and sleep quality. These potential confounders were not accounted for in the study, which limits the ability to attribute the observed associations solely to stress.

DISCUSSION

During the early stage of the COVID-19 pandemic, anxiety symptoms were reported in 28.8% and depressive symptoms in 16.5% of the general population in China [21].

In the literature review [22-25], no difference was found between the units where the medical personnel were working during the pandemic and their anxiety levels. The current study is considered that the anxiety of medical personnel increased due to having to provide simultaneous treatment and care to both adults and children, who are very different from each other in terms of their characteristics and needs.

This prevalence rate of poor sleep quality was higher than most of the studies that assessed sleep quality among healthcare workers. For example, in a sample of US doctors working in the emergency room, Machi et al. reported that the prevalence of poor sleep quality was 31% [26]. Another study in Pakistan reported that poor sleep quality was 37% among physicians [27]. A recent study in the region, in Saudi Arabia, reported that 51% of primary care physicians had poor sleep quality [28]. The higher prevalence of poor sleep quality in this study may be related to concerns related to the contagious nature of COVID-19. This is supported by a recent study, in China, of 180 medical staff who treated patients with COVID-19 infection that reported a higher mean PSQI

score of 8.6 ± 4.6 comparable with our results [29,30].

Conflict of Interest: No conflict of interest was declared by the authors.

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REFERENCES

1. Adams, J.G.; Walls, R.M. Supporting the Health Care Workforce during the COVID-19 Global Epidemic. *JAMA* 2020, 323, 1439–1440.
2. Shanafelt, T.; Ripp, J.; Trockel, M. Understanding and Addressing Sources of Anxiety among Health Care Professionals during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *JAMA* 2020, 323, 2133–2134.
3. El-Hage, W.; Hingray, C.; Lemogne, C.; Yroni, A.; Brunault, P.; Bienvenu, T.; Etain, B.; Paquet, C.; Gohier, B.; Bennabi, D.; et al. Health professionals facing the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic: What are the mental health risks? *Encephale* 2020, 46, 73–80.
4. Menendez C, Gonzalez R, Donnay F, Leke RGF. Avoiding indirect effects of COVID-19 on maternal and child health. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2020;8:e863–e864. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. WHO, author. Attacks on health care in the context of COVID-19. Geneva: WHO; [Sep 20, 2021]. <https://www.who.int/newsroom/feature-stories/detail/attacks-on-healthcare-in-the-context-of-covid-19>. [Google Scholar]
6. WHO, author. COVID-19 significantly impacts health services for noncommunicable diseases. Geneva: WHO; [September 19, 2021]. <https://www.who.int/newsroom/detail/01-06-2020-covid-19-significantly-impacts-health-services-for-noncommunicable-diseases>. [Google Scholar]
7. Papautsky EL, Hamlish T. Patient-reported treatment delays in breast cancer care during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Breast Cancer Res Trea*. 2020;184(1):249–254. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. Panagiotidis E. Nuclear medicine and oncology in the COVID-19 pandemic era. *Hell J Nucl Med*. 2020;23(Suppl):35–40. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
9. Park C, Sugand K, Nathwani D, et al. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on orthopedic trauma workload in a London level 1 trauma center: the “golden month” *Acta Orthop*. 2020;91(5):556–561. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
10. Passos L, Prazeres F. Impact on mental health due to COVID-19 pandemic: cross-sectional study in Portugal and Brazil. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(18):6794. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
11. Uta Lehmann, David Sanders A report on Community health workers: WHO [Internet][cited 2021 June 12]. Available from:https://www.who.int/hrh/documents/community_health_workers.pdf (2007) Google Scholar
12. COVID-19 Book of Five Response and containment measures for ANM, ASHA, wWW[Internet] [cited 2021 June 12]. Available from: [https://www.mohfw.gov.in/pdf/3Pocketbookof5_Covid19_27March.pdf\(2020\)](https://www.mohfw.gov.in/pdf/3Pocketbookof5_Covid19_27March.pdf(2020)) Google Scholar
13. WHO Report. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic. 2021; Available at: <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>.
14. Vittori, A.; Marinangeli, F.; Bignami, E.G.; Simonini, A.; Vergallo, A.; Fiore, G.; Petrucci, E.; Cascella, M.; Pedone, R. Analysis on burnout, job conditions, alexithymia, and other psychological symptoms in a sample of italian anesthesiologists and intensivists, assessed just before the COVID-19 pandemic: An AAROI-EMAC study. *Healthcare* 2022, 10, 1370.
15. Serrano-Ripoll, M.J.; Meneses-Echavez, J.F.; Ricci-Cabello, I.; Fraile-Navarro, D.;

- Fiol-deRoque, M.A.; Pastor-Moreno, G.; Castro,A.; Ruiz-Pérez, I.; Zamanillo Campos, R.; Gonçalves-Bradley, D.C. Impact of viral epidemic outbreaks on mental health of healthcare workers: A rapid systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Affect. Disord.* 2020, 277, 347–357.
16. Pacheco, J.P.; Giacomini, H.T.; Tam, W.W.; Ribeiro, T.B.; Arab, C.; Bezerra, I.M.; Pinasco, G.C. Mental health problems among medical students in Brazil: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Braz. J. Psychiatry* 2017, 39, 369–378.
 17. Busch, I.M.; Moretti, F.; Mazzi, M.; Wu, A.W.; Rimondini, M. What We Have Learned from Two Decades of Epidemics and Pandemics: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of the Psychological Burden of Frontline Healthcare Workers. *Psychother. Psychosom.* 2021, 90, 178–190.
 18. Dantzer, R. Stress theories and the somatization process. *L'encephale* 1995, 21, 3–9.
 19. ILO 2016. International Labour Organization 2016. Available online: https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/-/-ed_protect/-/-protrav/-/-safework/documents/publication/wcms_466547.pdf (accessed on 19 July 2023).
 20. von Elm E, Altman DG, Egger M, Pocock SJ, Gøtzsche PC, Vandenbroucke JP. The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. *Lancet* 2007 Oct;370(9596):1453-1457.
 21. Wang C, Pan R, Wan X, Tan Y, Xu L, McIntyre RS, et al. A longitudinal study on the mental health of general population during the COVID-19 epidemic in China. *Brain Behav Immun.* 2020;87:40–48. doi: 10.1016/j.bbi.2020.04.028.
 22. Huang JZ, Han MF, Luo TD, Ren AK, Zhou XP. Mental health survey of medical staff in a tertiary infectious disease hospital for COVID-19. *Zhonghua Lao Dong Wei Sheng Zhi Ye Bing Za Zhi* 2020;38:192-5.
 23. Tercan M, Bozkurt FT, Patmano G, Saraçoğlu G, Gür SC. Anxiety and depression differences between the nurses working at a COVID-19 pandemic hospital. *Medical Science and Discovery* 2020;7:526-31.
 24. Uyaroğlu OA, Başaran NÇ, Ozisik L, Karahan S, Tanriover MD, Guven GS, Oz SG. Evaluation of the effect of COVID-19 pandemic on anxiety severity of physicians working in the internal medicine department of a tertiary care hospital: a cross-sectional survey. *Intern Med J* 2020;50:1350-8.
 25. Zhang R, Hou T, Kong X, Wang G, Wang H, Xu S, Xu J, He J, Xiao L, Wang Y, Du J, Huang Y, Su T, Tang Y. Effects of region, epidemic stage, and demographic characteristics on sleep quality and mental disturbances among health care workers during COVID-19 outbreak. *Europe PMC.* 2020. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-23260/v1>.
 26. Machi MS, Staum M, Callaway CW, Moore C, Jeong K, Suyama J, Patterson PD, Hostler D (2012) The relationship between shift work, sleep, and cognition in career emergency physicians. *Acad Emerg Med* 19(1):85–91. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1553-2712.2011.01254.x>
 27. Surani AA, Surani A, Zahid S, Ali S, Farhan R, Surani S (2015) To assess sleep quality among Pakistani junior physicians (house officers): a cross-sectional study. *Ann Med Health Sci Res* 5(5):329–333. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2141-9248.165246>
 28. Alhifzi S, Al-Ghonimy A, Al Aboudi M, Al Abdullah R, Olaish A, BaHammam AS (2018) Assessment of sleep quality, daytime sleepiness, and depression among emergency physicians working in shifts. *J Nat Sci Med* 1:17–21. https://doi.org/10.4103/JNSM.JNSM_8_18
 29. Xiao H, Zhang Y, Kong D, Li S, Yang N (2020) The effects of social support on

- sleep quality of medical staff treating patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in January and February 2020 in China. *Med Sci Monit* 26:e923549. <https://doi.org/10.12659/MSM.923549>
30. Merga H, Fufa T (2019) Impacts of working environment and benefits packages on the health professionals' job satisfaction in selected public health facilities in eastern Ethiopia: using principal component analysis. *BMC Health Serv Res* 19(1):494. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-019-4317-5>